

GLOBAL DATABASE TRANSFORMATION IN EDUCATION

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Annotation: In this article, the importance and relevance of creating a large database in the process of convergence of educational services, as well as their theoretical and practical aspects, are highlighted, and opinions are expressed on this topic. Within the framework of the approach based on the economic directions of the knowledge economy, specific theoretical information is given on the formation of competencies for the purpose of training future specialists in the economic direction.

Key words: Secondary education, higher education, school education, convergence, knowledge economy, pedagogical skills, database, convergence process, educational services.

The new trends in the socio-economic development of modern countries are first of all the innovative economy based on the idea of Y. Schumpeter [14], the network economy advanced in the concepts presented in the scientific works of J. Hawkins called the economy of knowledge or the theory of creative economy [15], and D. The digital economy introduced by Tapscott [17] consists of In the analysis of the definitions given to the concept of knowledge economy, it can be observed that it is approached as an economic relationship. For example, YV Smagin: "... knowledge economy is a modern economic attitude based on experts who can introduce new technologies. In this case, new relations arise in the solution of local and global issues and in the introduction of tomorrow's technologies into the economy" [18] - he describes.

In education, the transformation of a large database using the convergence of the received information about the state of formation occurs. In the process of transformation of the educational process, a large database is definitely formed. This database provides the ability to take into account the factors of "optimism" and "pessimism" in the answers received as a result of an intellectual inquiry, and to ensure the security of the database when improving the quality of education with the development of socio-economic processes (2- picture).

Figure 1. The transformation of global database formation in education

As we can see from the picture, it is necessary to implement a number of measures for the stable operation of electronic resources of the digitized educational system. These include Hadoop security, cloud security, monitoring and auditing, key management, and data anonymization. The application of these security parameters is in the management of electronic systems of the regional industry distinguished by its importance. This, in turn, leads to the creation of a structural scheme for the implementation of active communication with the Exponent MBBT of the information model of the regional industrial structure. We can see this in Figure 3 below.

To conclude, in the research, we attach importance to the information supply to obtain the practical results and calculated indicators of the model system solution of the convergence of the educational system. Materials and documents related to the development of the educational structure, improvement of its infrastructure, documents from statistical reports, organizations, and the results of scientific research are used as a basis for obtaining general information.

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